

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Table S1. Omnibus tests (Type-III; Satterthwaite d.f.; PB = parametric bootstrap)

Variables: mean force (meanF), force variability (CV), and EMG–EMG coherence (area rate). p-values shown as <0.001 when rounded to 0.000. Effect sizes: partial eta-squared (η^2) and partial omega-squared (ω^2).

Term	Measure	df (num, den)	F (lmer)	p (lmer)	η^2	ω^2
condition	meanF	4, 317.000	4.403	0.002	0.053	0.049
condition	CV	4, 316.972	3.247	0.012	0.039	0.036
condition	area-rate	4, 1460.7	205.6	<0.001	0.65	0.649
condition: freq	area-rate	12, 1459.9	29.11	<0.001	0.728	0.727

Table S2. Significant Omnibus tests (Type-III; Satterthwaite d.f.; PB = parametric bootstrap)

Variables: High-pass-rectified EMG–EMG coherence (area-rate). p-values shown as <0.001 when rounded to 0.000. Effect sizes: partial eta-squared (ηp^2) and partial omega-squared (ωp^2).

Term	Measure	df (num, den)	F (lmer)	p (lmer)	ηp^2	ωp^2
condition	area-rate	4, 1461.96	110.922	<0.001	0.525	0.524
condition: freq	area-rate	12, 1461.03	14.193	<0.001	0.579	0.579

Table S3. Flight-day order sensitivity analysis.

LMMs were re-fit using only conditions collected on the same day (0.25, 0.50, 0.75, and 1 g) to eliminate between-session order as a confound. F-tests are Type III with Satterthwaite d.f. η^2 = partial eta-squared.

DV	Term	numDF	F	p	η^2	Sig.
Mean force	Gravity	3	6.69	< 0.001	0.074	***
	Gravity \times Task	6	0.60	0.730	0.014	
	Gravity \times Hand	3	0.46	0.710	0.005	
CV of force	Gravity	3	1.29	0.278	0.015	
	Gravity \times Task	6	0.46	0.835	0.011	
EMG coherence (interference)	Gravity	3	163.98	< 0.001	0.304	***
	Gravity \times Freq	9	26.53	< 0.001	0.175	***
	Gravity \times Task	6	2.57	0.018	0.014	*
EMG coherence (HP-rectified)	Gravity	3	76.60	< 0.001	0.170	***
	Gravity \times Freq	9	11.34	< 0.001	0.083	***
	Gravity \times Task	6	1.37	0.223	0.007	
MRL	Gravity	3	0.30	0.823	0.008	
AE (omnibus)	Gravity	3	0.42	0.741	0.010	
AE (90° only)	Gravity	3	1.90	0.149	0.147	
CRP-SD	Gravity	3	0.20	0.894	0.005	

Note: The within-session subset includes only data from the partial-gravity flight day (0.25, 0.50, 0.75 g collected in-flight; 1 g collected pre-flight on the same day). The 0 g condition, tested on a separate day, is excluded. All model specifications match the primary analyses except for the reduced number of gravity levels. The covariate analysis (adding flight day to the full model) produced identical results to the base model for all 23 gravity related terms and is not shown.

Figure S1. High-pass-rectified EMG coherence (area-rate) across gravity by frequency band.

Violin and box plots of EMG coherence (area-rate) at each gravity level, faceted by frequency band (α : 5-13, β : 13-30, low- γ : 30-60, and high- γ : 60-100 Hz). Points are subject means (collapsed across tasks within band); violins show the between-subject distribution; boxes show median and IQR (whiskers = $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$).

EMG coherence across gravity levels by task and frequency band

Figure S2. EMG coherence (area-rate) across gravity levels by task and frequency band.

Violin and box plots of EMG coherence (area-rate) at each gravity level (0, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, and 1 g), faceted by frequency band (rows: α : 5–13 Hz, β : 13–30 Hz, low- γ : 30–60 Hz, and high- γ : 60–100 Hz) and task (columns: 0°, 90°, and 180°). Each filled circle represents one participant's mean coherence for a given gravity \times task \times band cell; thin gray lines connect the same participant across

gravity levels to show individual trajectories. Violins indicate the between-subject distribution; boxes show the median and interquartile range (IQR; whiskers = $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$). The decrease in coherence with decreasing gravity is visible across all three tasks, with the largest effects in the α and β bands and the smallest in the high- γ band, consistent with the omnibus Gravity \times Frequency interaction reported in the main text.